

WELLNESS ACROSS BORDERS: A STUDY OF MEDICAL TOURISM POTENTIAL IN INDIA

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Abstract:

Globally, the medical tourism business has grown steadily in recent years. Patients are destined to seek cross-border healthcare as the whole population grows more aware of healthcare possibilities and as excellent healthcare rises as a priority in the thoughts of the majority of people. High-quality health care, specific treatment alternatives, rapid service possibility for travel, and cost are thus the key reasons for medical tourism. Access to healthcare may lead to medical travel in areas where quality treatment is unavailable; for others, cost-effectiveness may be a factor. India has developed as one of the most sought-after medical tourism destinations in the world, owing to its high-value proposition in terms of excellent healthcare, a pool of experts, and the availability of alternative therapy methods such as Ayurveda and yoga. This paper is an attempt to assess the capability of medical tourism in India and to emphasize the obstacles that may arise. This article covers the idea of medical tourism briefly and focuses on treatments that need medical or surgical intervention. Also included is a brief examination of the force and demand for these particulars in the moment's global environment.

Keywords: Medical, Tourism, Global, India, Healthcare, Treatment.

Introduction: - Medical tourism is gaining increasing traction in contemporary society. Individuals from various global regions journey to foreign nations primarily for medical procedures such as dental care, surgical interventions, and fertility therapies. People seeking treatment often want to combine it with a well-planned vacation. Medical tourism is taking advantage of services the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) provides while traveling overseas for health care services such as dental treatment, cosmetic surgery, and fertility treatment.

Traveling for medical reasons is not a new thing. Many heroic journeys are narrated in ancient stories, folklore, and fables to benefit others, generally the monarch or queen, in search of potions and remedies. Eternal beauty and immortality have the same incentives. Pursuing mysteries and supernatural legends is not confined to one culture but reaches across all cultures, and the population is aging.

As per a recent study, individuals who reside in urban areas tend to have access to top-tier medical professionals who can perform procedures such as knee, hip, and dental surgeries at a premium cost, akin to that of a luxurious five-star hotel. There is a growing trend of individuals from countries such as the United States and Europe seeking medical treatment in India, primarily due to the potential for cost savings. Apart from exorbitant prices, procedures like surgery can last more than six months, years, or even longer, which causes clients to seek medical care in other countries like India. Many health insurance companies do not cover cosmetic surgery, so many rich people in developed countries decide to seek treatment abroad. It is exciting to see how health insurers will promote medical tourism as a cost-cutting option in the coming years.

Most emerging market hospitals add flavors to medical facilities and provide customers with packages that include all facilities and services from medical, travel, and generous services to local attractions in a single service. We appreciate cost control. Medical tourism is seen in the same way as tourism in that it provides medical care and vacation, so the gap between hospitals and hospitality organizations is gradually closing.

According to McKinsey, "the primary purpose of the people is to acquire medical treatment in an overseas country by traveling, exclusive of disaster tourists, wellness tourists, emigrants looking for care in their own country, patients traveling to neighboring countries which are closest accessible to their countries."

The graphic below will help to clarify the above definition.

Fig 1. Source: McKinsey Quarterly, Medical Travel Market Mapping, 2008

Objective of Study

The primary goals of this research are as follows:

1. The objective is to examine the present condition of the medical tourism industry in India.
2. This study examines the primary factors that propel and constrain the phenomenon of medical tourism in India.
3. The present study aims to examine diverse external environmental factors that directly impact the medical tourism industry in India.

Methodology

The research methodology employed in this study is characterized by a demonstrative, exploratory, and informal approach, which is divided into distinct sections. The study obtained information and sources from various academic materials such as books, publications, periodicals, academic papers, and e-journals. Additionally, reports from reputable organizations such as the United Nations World Report, Ministry of Tourism Report, World Travel & Tourism Council Report, and World Travel & Tourism Council Report were utilised.

Fig 2. Source WHO Patient Safety Programme 2013. Conceptual Framework of Globalization and Medical Tourism

Literature Review:

- According to **(Frechtling, 1997)** Medical tourism refers to the movement of people from wealthy nations to other (particularly poor) countries to receive low-cost medical or surgical care.
- According to **Connell (2006)**, Medical tourism also provided clinical travelers with the hazard to acquire medical offerings in a timely way, whereas they would have to wait for a longer amount of time if they sought treatment in their home nations. Furthermore, several initiatives (improved

medical facilities, effective communication networks, and better transportation facilities) implemented by developing country governments have resulted in a significant increase in medical tourism.

- **(Lunt & Carrera, 2010)** Discussed that It has been established that patients from affluent nations can benefit from medical tourism for a wide range of medical treatments. Furthermore, persons suffering from rare genetic illnesses may benefit from medical tourism since medical institutions in developing countries have a better understanding of this treatment. Medical tourists would also undergo a variety of medical procedures (such as psychiatry, convalescent care, and alternative therapy). About 50 countries have already declared medical tourism as the main industry.
- According to (Sultana, S., Haque, A., Momen, A., & Yasmin, F. 2014), medical tourists prioritize quality and cost of service when deciding on medical practice. increase. Moreover, in contrast to other aspects that influence destination decisions, visitor attitudes are less relevant, but they value the competitiveness of the location. For a country Like India to turn out to be an attractive and aggressive medical Tourism vacation spot in the technology of globalization, measures ought to be taken to reduce costs while preserving great providers.

The following are the top medical tourism destinations in India:

Gradually, India is becoming one of the very prominent medical tourism destinations. Because of its superb medical services that are similar to those planted in fat nations at a bit of the cost. For many years, tourists to India have come not just to enjoy the sights and sounds of the nation, but also to receive healthcare and medical treatments. This might be due to healthcare being inaccessible due to either insufficient infrastructure or extremely expensive medical prices. Medical tourism in India is likely to grow as people become more aware of alternative treatments. Better amenities are expected to enhance the number of visitors to the nation this year. Mumbai, Delhi, Chennai, Bangalore, Hyderabad, and Kolkata are among the top medical tourism destinations in India.

- **New Delhi:** A variety of private hospitals in the country's capital offer specialized services to overseas patients, including sophisticated surgical packages, eye surgery, cardiac care, and neurosurgery. Visit the Jama Masjid or the Lotus Temple while you're in town for therapy to refresh your mind and body (Velu, 2018).
- **Chennai** is one of India's most well-known treatment centers. Chennai is known as India's fitness capital, and it receives roughly 200 patients from all over the world for bone marrow transplants, heart transplantation, eye surgery, hip replacement, and other procedures. To rejuvenate yourself physically and spiritually, you may wish to visit Marina Beach, the Thalalankuppam Pier, Guindy National Park, or Queens Land when traveling across the town for scientific purposes (Velu, 2018).
- **Mumbai,** Among India's finest medical tourism destinations, this healthcare destination features multiple super specialty hospitals and a weight-loss and orthopedics research and diagnostic center. There are many cosmetic surgery clinics in Mumbai, as well as Ayurvedic remedies. Top-tier treatment facilities and a plethora of private institutions have propelled Mumbai to the top of the list of medical treatment destinations. Take a walk on the adjacent beach to re-energize yourself. You may also go to the Gateway of India and other tourist attractions in and around South Mumbai.
- **Goa:** Foreign travelers commonly visit Goa for enjoyment, and it has now turned into a medical vacation destination as well. Goa's natural landscape, popularity among visitors, and government aid in promoting health and well-being have all contributed to the state's emergence as a medical center. When traveling the city for medical purposes, you may need to visit the shorelines or the Bonda Wildlife Park, among other sites, to refresh your body and spirit (Velu, 2018).

Numerous medical visiting and tour operators have emerged across the nation to provide comprehensive medical tourism services after discovering how strong the health and medical categories are becoming. Undoubtedly, medical tourism is an economic tool that can help countries like India grow their economies. Direct benefits include increased income, employment opportunities, and tourism investments. The spillover effect that leads to the growth of other industries is an example of indirect benefits (Bhowmick, 2018). Although the benefits may seem small, the spillover effects

can impact various economic areas such as boosting tourism-related living conditions, education demand, the requirement for associated higher education, and sub-industry growth

Medical Tourism in India: Where Are We Now?

Following the COVID-19 outbreak, India is turning into the following pinnacle clinical tourism vacation spot. Soon after the COVID-19 epidemic, India becomes capable of creating its pandemic vaccine instead of uploading it from different nations. This highlights India`s technological and genetic advancements. India has been a famous clinical tourism vacation spot for greater than a decade, with lots of human beings journeying to the United States every year for treatment. The bulk of traffic come from Asian and African nations. People so-referred to as bubble nations inclusive of the United States, the United Kingdom, and Australia account for a minor share of the population. In 2019, around 697,453 remote places travelers got here to India for clinical treatment, in line with data.

This number decreased as a result of the **coronavirus pandemic**, which resulted in lockdowns and airline cancellations between several Asian and African nations. However, the overall visitor influx is presently progressively increasing. With the lifting of worldwide travel restrictions and lockdowns, Indian medical tourism hopes to advance in a lot of important instances such as organ transplants and other serious cases. The medical tourism industry in India is set to improve in the post-Covid era. Due to the way the country handled the epidemic, this is the case. Hospitals, physicians, and paramedics have handled the current pandemic incredibly well, resulting in a ratio of fewer than **1.5 percent of total patients to death cases**. Another crucial reason is that many health care personnel have received COVID-19 vaccinations. This implies that medical personnel are secure from infection and will not transfer it.

Medical treatment cost comparison (2021) (US \$)

Medical Treatment	India	Colombia	Mexico	Thailand	Ukraine
Angioplasty	5700	11700	8500	10938	4000
Heart bypass	7000	11200	25000	17188	22000
Heart Valve Replacement	10000	20000	23000	21188	7000
Cataract eye	1400	2000	2500	1800	1300

Fig. 3 Average cost of Treatment <https://www.Medicaltourism.Com/Compare-Prices>. Retrieved April 3, 2022

Advantages of Medical Tourism

- ✓ Treatment by a specialist
- ✓ Destination for both treatment and relaxation
- ✓ Medical professionals are easily accessible.
- ✓ Consultation at a low cost
- ✓ Low-cost therapy
- ✓ There is less treatment waiting time.
- ✓ Advanced equipment is available.

Disadvantages of Medical Tourism in India

- ✓ **Medical malpractice:** Although hospitals provide medical malpractice insurance, misdiagnosis during treatment can lead to unexpected results. And since most tourists are not familiar with India's legal system, additional complications may arise.
- ✓ **Insurance Coverage:** The sort of medical care you get determines your insurance coverage. So, before seeking any treatment, make sure you are aware of all the facts to prevent any needless spending during your stay abroad. Furthermore, This can be difficult as medical travelers are unaware of the legal issues and because legal procedures in countries like the US and UK are very open.
- ✓ **Post-Operation Recovery:** Most of the time, after undergoing medical treatments, patients must return to the same hospital for routine health checks. However, problems emerge when the recovery period after the surgery is prolonged, and in such circumstances, medical tourists in India must arrange their accommodations outside the hospital.

- ✓ **Transportation Costs:** It is usually suggested that medical tourists travel with someone while seeking medical care in another country. However, this increases the cost of travel, lodging, and other expenses.

Recommendations

- Improve infrastructures in the country, such as additional super-specialty hospitals, a stronger rail-road network within the country, and air transportation within and beyond the country.
- Take the appropriate efforts to halt or minimize the process of medical brain drain.
- Medical tourists may be granted a visa upon arrival. The Indian embassy in a foreign nation can collaborate with local hospitals and officials.

Conclusion

Medical tourism is one of the world's and India's fastest-growing service industries. India has earned a competitive edge in several medical facilities and is also becoming a popular tourism destination. To further grow this industry, steps must be done. This necessitates constant and ongoing efforts on the part of both the government and the population. Medical tourism may be a lucrative industry that generates both foreign currency and jobs for its citizens. Despite the numerous hurdles that the Indian medical tourism business has, such as competitiveness, infrastructure, brain drain, follow-up issues, and so on, the industry has all the potential to expand to the number one position in terms of attracting international visitors.

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